

Supplementary Appendix: Quantitative Estimation of the Muscle-Mass Decline Required to Meaningfully Bias Creatinine-Based eGFR and Supplementary Methods for Detecting Treatment-Induced Changes in Endogenous Creatinine Generation

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Box S1. Quantitative estimation of the muscle-mass decline required to meaningfully bias creatinine-based eGFR

To illustrate the magnitude of skeletal muscle-mass loss that would be required to explain the observed between-group difference in annual change in eGFRcr in the TEMPO3:4 trial (-0.98 ml/min/1.73 m²),¹ we performed a quantitative estimation under conservative assumptions. Specifically, we considered a hypothetical scenario in which the entire observed treatment effect of tolvaptan on eGFRcr is attributable to treatment-induced reductions in endogenous creatinine generation rather than true preservation of GFR.

We based this estimation on representative participant characteristics from the tolvaptan arm at mid-follow-up: a male individual aged 40.5 years, with a height of 1.78 m and a body weight of 79 kg.¹ Using the Du Bois formula,² the corresponding body-surface area is approximately 1.93 m². The reported between-group difference in annual change in eGFRcr of -0.98 ml/min/1.73 m² therefore corresponds to an absolute difference of approximately 1.09 ml/min after un-indexing for body-surface area ($0.98 \times (1.93 / 1.73)$).

To translate this into a corresponding change in daily creatinine excretion, an estimate of plasma creatinine concentration representative of the observation period is required. Under steady-state conditions, daily creatinine excretion (mg/day) is given by the product of creatinine clearance (ml/min), plasma creatinine concentration (mg/ml), and time (minutes per day). For this calculation, creatinine clearance was approximated by eGFRcr after un-indexing for body-surface area, consistent with standard practice in physiological approximations. Assuming a linear decline in GFR over the 3-year follow-up period, the midpoint eGFRcr is approximately 77.3 ml/min/1.73 m². Using the 2021 race-free CKD-EPI creatinine-based GFR-estimating equation,³ this corresponds to a plasma creatinine concentration of 1.21 mg/dl for a male of this age. Based on this concentration, the between-group difference in eGFRcr (after de-indexing for BSA) corresponds to an annual difference in daily creatinine excretion of approximately 19 mg per day (1.09 ml/min \times 0.0121 mg/ml \times 1440 min/day).

Established relationships between urinary creatinine excretion and skeletal muscle mass indicate that each gram of daily creatinine excretion corresponds to approximately 17.1 kg of skeletal muscle.⁴ Applying this relationship, the estimated reduction in creatinine excretion translates into a loss of approximately 0.33 kg of skeletal muscle per year. For a typical male individual with a total skeletal muscle mass of approximately 31.6 kg,⁵ this corresponds to a relative decline of approximately 1% per year.

This calculation demonstrates that a qualitatively small and physiologically plausible change in muscle mass could fully account for the observed between-group difference in eGFRcr in TEMPO3:4.¹ While this does not imply that such muscle loss occurred in TEMPO3:4, it illustrates that even modest treatment-related changes in creatinine generation could, in principle, meaningfully bias creatinine-based estimates of GFR in clinical trials.

Methods S1. General framework

The magnitude of change in creatinine generation required to confound creatinine-based estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR_{cr}) in clinical trials with tolvaptan, as demonstrated in **Box S1**, is small and biologically plausible. Confidence in the interpretation of creatinine-based trial outcomes depends on whether such changes can be empirically detected or confidently excluded within feasible study designs. Across all approaches considered in this appendix, we define a common target effect corresponding to a 0.5% change in endogenous creatinine generation over a six-month interval. This threshold is derived from our earlier estimation that a sustained yearly change of approximately 1% would be sufficient to fully account for the treatment effect on eGFR_{cr} reported in TEMPO3:4,¹ thereby providing a clinically meaningful benchmark for detectability over shorter time horizons.

Sample size calculations are based on comparisons of the mean change in the relevant measurement between intervention and placebo groups over a six-month period. All estimates assume an independent-samples comparison between treatment arms, 80% statistical power, and a two-sided α of 0.05.

For each method, required sample sizes are derived based on assumptions regarding (i) the baseline magnitude of the underlying biological quantity (e.g., the total creatine pool size or a representative value for eGFR_{cr}) and (ii) the within-subject biological variation, reflecting natural short-term fluctuations within individuals observed across repeated measurements. Method-specific assumptions and their empirical justification are detailed in the corresponding sections below. Illustrative intermediate computations are additionally provided where appropriate to facilitate transparency and reproducibility of the sample size estimates. Intermediate values shown in equations are rounded for readability; final sample size estimates were calculated using unrounded values and rounded only after per-group estimates were obtained and converted to total sample sizes.

Methods S2. MRI/MRS-based assessment of total creatine pool

Reproducibility studies combining Dixon MRI with ¹H- and ³¹P-magnetic resonance spectroscopy have demonstrated low within-subject variability for repeated assessments of the constituent measures that jointly determine total creatine pool size, including muscle volume and intramuscular creatine and phosphocreatine concentrations.⁶⁻⁹ Although these studies do not directly report repeatability of the total creatine pool expressed in grams, their findings provide an empirical basis for approximating the variability of longitudinal change in this composite measure.

For repeated measurements, the standard deviation of individual baseline-to-follow-up changes depends on both the cross-sectional variability of the measurement and the correlation between repeated observations, according to:

$$SD_{\Delta} = \sqrt{2\sigma^2(1 - \rho)}$$

where σ denotes the cross-sectional standard deviation and ρ the correlation between repeated measurements. For the present calculation, we assumed a moderate correlation of $\rho = 0.5$ between baseline and 6-month measurements across individuals and conservatively specified the standard deviation of individual baseline-to-6-month changes in total endogenous creatine pool as 1.0 g, reflecting the relatively low within-subject variability reported across the constituent imaging measures.

Assuming a baseline pool of 135 g in a 79 kg male,¹⁰ a 0.5% change over six months corresponds to an absolute difference of:

$$0.005 \times 135 = 0.675 \text{ g}$$

Under these assumptions, sample size per group for the independent-samples comparison was calculated as:

$$n_{\text{group}} = \frac{2 \times (z_{1-\alpha/2} + z_{1-\beta})^2 \times SD_{\Delta}^2}{\delta^2} = \frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 1.0^2}{0.675^2} \approx 35$$

corresponding to a total sample size of approximately 70 participants that would be required to detect this difference.

Methods S3. Stable isotope dilution techniques

Stable isotope dilution techniques (e.g., using [¹³C]- or [²H₃]-creatinine) provide a direct method for estimating total body creatine pool size.¹¹⁻¹³ In contrast to imaging-based approaches, where repeated measurements can be performed under tightly standardised acquisition conditions, these methods are subject to greater variability arising from urinary loss of tracer, incomplete equilibration across body creatine pools, variability introduced during sample processing and analyses, and day-to-day biological variation related to diet and physical activity.¹¹⁻¹³

For the present calculation, variability in baseline-to-6-month changes was approximated using the repeated-measures framework described in **Methods S2**. Assuming a moderate correlation of $\rho = 0.4$ between baseline and follow-up measurements, the standard deviation of individual baseline-to-6-month changes in total creatine pool size was conservatively specified as 1.9 g.

Applying the detectability threshold of 0.675 g defined in **Methods S2**:

$$n_{\text{group}} = \frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 1.9^2}{0.675^2} \approx 125$$

corresponding to a total sample size of approximately 250 participants that would be required to detect this difference.

Methods S4. Longitudinal discordance between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys}

An indirect, regulator-endorsed approach for assessing treatment-related changes in creatinine generation is joint evaluation of creatinine-based and cystatin C-based eGFR.^{14,15} Cystatin C is produced at a relatively constant rate by all nucleated cells¹⁶ and is therefore largely independent of muscle mass and creatinine generation. While cystatin C concentrations show less person-to-person variability in production than creatinine,¹⁷ they can still be influenced by several non-GFR determinants, including inflammation,¹⁸ adiposity,¹⁹ thyroid function,²⁰ cigarette smoking,¹⁸ and glucocorticoid exposure.²¹ Nonetheless, both the EMA and FDA recommend measuring cystatin C as a confirmatory test and derive cystatin C-based eGFR (eGFR_{cys}) when drug-related changes in endogenous creatinine generation cannot be excluded.^{14,15}

Joint assessment of eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} trajectories enables quantification of longitudinal discordance between the two estimates, which primarily arises from non-GFR determinants of each marker, including deviations in creatinine generation beyond the variability expected based on age and sex.²² As such, discordance between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} trajectories can be used to infer longitudinal changes in endogenous creatinine generation.

Previous studies have reported within-subject biological variability of approximately 5.5% for eGFR_{cr} and 3.5% for eGFR_{cys} over short time intervals.^{23–25} At a representative mean eGFR_{cr} of 80 ml/min/1.73 m², approximating the mean baseline eGFR_{cr} reported in TEMPO3:4,¹ these correspond to standard deviations of approximately 4.4 and 2.8 ml/min/1.73 m², respectively.

The variance of the discordance between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} can be approximated as:

$$\text{Var}(D) = \sigma_{cr}^2 + \sigma_{cys}^2 - 2\rho\sigma_{cr}\sigma_{cys}$$

Assuming a moderate correlation of $\rho = 0.5$ between repeated measurements, this corresponds to an approximate standard deviation of:

$$\text{SD}(D) = \sqrt{4.4^2 + 2.8^2 - 2 \times 0.5 \times 4.4 \times 2.8} \approx 3.9 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2$$

for individual baseline-to-6-month changes in the discordance between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys}.

At this level of kidney function, the detectability threshold corresponding to a 0.5% relative change in discordance between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} trajectories is estimated at:

$$0.005 \times 80 = 0.4 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2$$

Sample size per group for the independent-samples comparison was thus calculated as:

$$n_{\text{group}} = \frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 3.9^2}{0.4^2} \approx 1,459$$

corresponding to a total sample size of approximately 2,918 participants that would be required to detect this difference.

Methods S5. Longitudinal 24-hour urinary creatinine excretion

Measurement of creatinine excretion in longitudinally collected 24-hour urine provides another indirect approach to assessing endogenous creatinine generation, typically operationalized as creatinine clearance. This approach was not emphasised in regulatory guidance by the EMA and FDA,^{14,15} likely due to the logistical challenges associated with 24-hour urine collection in clinical trials. Furthermore, patients on tolvaptan willing to complete such collections may represent a subset that would not be generalisable to the broader ADPKD population.²⁶

For the present calculation, within-subject variability in 24-hour urinary creatinine excretion was informed by serial collection studies conducted under controlled conditions.²⁷ Variability in baseline-to-6-month changes in endogenous creatinine generation was approximated using the repeated-measures framework described in **Methods S2**. Assuming a correlation of $\rho = 0.4$ between baseline and 6-month measurements, the standard deviation of individual baseline-to-6-month changes was conservatively set at 1.5 g.

Applying the detectability threshold of 0.675 g defined in **Methods S2**:

$$n_{\text{group}} = \frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 1.5^2}{0.675^2} \approx 78$$

corresponding to a total sample size of approximately 156 participants that would be required to detect this difference.

This estimate should be interpreted with caution. Available variability estimates are derived from highly controlled settings in which urine collection, diet, and participant behaviour were tightly standardised.²⁷ Under free-living conditions, particularly in tolvaptan-treated patients with large urine volumes, within-subject biological variability is likely to be substantially higher, implying that the true sample size required to exclude modest treatment-induced changes may be considerably larger.

Methods S6. Detectability in the TEMPO3:4 trial

The sample size calculations presented above are based on detection of a 0.5% change in endogenous creatinine generation over a six-month interval using independent-samples comparisons. In longitudinal clinical trials with repeated measurements, such as TEMPO3:4,¹ treatment effects can instead be assessed through divergence between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} trajectories over time. Under this framework, the minimum detectable cumulative effect depends on (i) the joint variability of eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys}, (ii) their correlation over time, and (iii) the number of participants remaining under observation at later time points. Because cumulative divergence is assessed at the end of follow-up, statistical power is effectively determined by the smallest risk set.

Using the within-subject variability estimates described in **Methods S4**, and assuming a representative mean eGFR of 80 ml/min/1.73 m², the corresponding standard deviations for eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} are approximately 4.4 and 2.8 ml/min/1.73 m², respectively. Assuming a conservative correlation of $\rho = 0.3$ between longitudinal changes in eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} to account for progressive discordance due to non-GFR determinants, this corresponds to an approximate standard deviation of:

$$SD(D) = \sqrt{4.4^2 + 2.8^2 - 2 \times 0.3 \times 4.4 \times 2.8} \approx 4.5 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2$$

The detectable cumulative divergence at three years was estimated by solving for the value of δ yielding a per-group sample size approximately equal to the smallest risk set remaining under observation in TEMPO3:4¹ (approximately 350 participants in the placebo arm at 36 months of follow-up):

$$n_{\text{group}} = \frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 4.5^2}{\delta^2} \approx 350$$

Rearranging for δ gives:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 4.5^2}{n_{\text{group}}}}$$

Using $n_{\text{group}} = 350$:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 4.5^2}{350}} \approx 0.94 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2$$

At this level of kidney function, the detectable cumulative discordance between eGFR_{cr} and eGFR_{cys} corresponds to a relative change of:

$$\frac{0.94 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2}{80 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2} \times 100\% \approx 1.2\%$$

over three years. Assuming approximately linear accumulation of discordance over time, this corresponds to an average detectable discordance of approximately:

$$\frac{1.2\%}{6} = 0.2\%$$

per six-month interval of follow-up between eGFRcr and eGFRcys trajectories.

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